

X-ray Absorption measurements at a bending magnet beamline with an Everhart-Thornley detector: A monolayer of $\text{Ho}_3\text{N@C}_{80}$ on graphene

Wei Chuang Lee,¹ Ryunosuke Sagehashi,¹ Yang Zhang,² Alexey A. Popov,² Matthias Muntwiler,³ and Thomas Greber¹

¹Physik-Institut, University of Zürich, CH-8057 Zürich, Switzerland

²Leibniz-Institute for Solid State and Materials Research (IFW), D-01069 Dresden, Germany

³Swiss Light Source, Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI), CH-5232 Villigen, Switzerland

(*Electronic mail: weichuang.lee@physik.uzh.ch)

(Dated: 11 July 2022)

X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) is used for measuring monolayer quantities of $\text{Ho}_3\text{N@C}_{80}$ endofullerene molecules on graphene at a low flux bending magnet beamline. The total electron yield is measured with an Everhart-Thornley detector. This approach decreases with respect to sample current measurements with the same noise level the data acquisition time and radiation dose by a factor of 25. As the first application of this set-up we report temperature-dependent measurements of the Ho M_{45} edge with per mille accuracy. This documents the advantages and capabilities of an Everhart-Thornley detector for XAS measurements under low x-ray flux.

X-ray absorption is a method for the investigation of matter with the resolution of the elemental constitution of a sample. The method is particularly sensitive for resonant inner shell excitations like $2p \rightarrow 3d$ or $3p \rightarrow 4f$ transitions, where submonolayer sensitivity may be obtained. Here we report the implementation of an Everhart-Thornley (ET) detection scheme for total electron yield that enables high quality XAS at low photon flux, which is mandatory for radiation sensitive samples.

We apply the ET electron yield detection scheme for x-ray absorption in monolayer quantities of $\text{Ho}_3\text{N@C}_{80}$ endohedral fullerenes at the Ho M_5 and M_4 edges. Molecules like endofullerenes are candidate components for molecular spintronics and electronics where XAS may reveal conformation and magnetism of the endohedral unit¹. In the present XAS application we investigate possible changes in endohedral orientation with temperature, where it is known that the average orientation of monolayer endofullerenes may change between 30 K and room temperature².

Figure 1 shows the Everhart-Thornley measurement setup at the Photoemission and Atomic Resolution Laboratory (PEARL) beamline at the Swiss light source³. The x-ray absorption causes electron emission which is proportional to the photon flux the x-ray absorption cross-section and the electron attenuation length in the target. In the total electron yield (TEY) measurement mode, the emitted electrons may be measured with the sample current, or as we show here with an Everhart-Thornley (ET) detector that is commonly used in secondary electron microscopes (SEM's) and for detection of other kinds of low energy electron currents in the vacuum⁴. The inset shows a measurement of the L_3 edge XAS of a Cu(111) crystal with the sample current and the simultaneously detected scintillation light in the ET detector from Staib instruments. The two signals are proportional which indicates that the ET current is qualitatively the same as the TEY. The relative standard deviation of the sample current I_S at photon energies between 910 and 925 eV is 5 times larger than that of I_{ET} . Apparently, the sample current cannot be measured in the shot-noise limit, but is affected by all kinds of noise at the beamline, while the ET setup is stable and re-

FIG. 1. Schematic of the measurement setup. X-rays illuminate the sample and the concomitant secondary electrons are collected by an Everhart-Thornley detector with a collector grid voltage $V_G = 20$ V. After the grid, the electrons are accelerated to the scintillator at $V_{Sc} = 6.5$ kV. A photomultiplier tube behind a standard view port for visible light detects the scintillator light outside the vacuum. The inset shows the Cu(111) L_3 edge measured with the ET detector current I_{ET} (red) and the sample current I_S (green). The two currents are proportional to each other, though the noise of the sample current is significantly higher than the ET detector current.

quires with the present settings 25 times lower measurement time for the same relative standard deviation of the measured currents. This also implies that the radiation dose for a given noise level scales with this number which opens opportunities for precise investigations of radiation sensitive systems. We chose detection via a scintillator and a photomultiplier tube (PMT), instead of a channeltron in order to have a detector servicing that does not involve the break of the vacuum. The instrument viewports are shielded from unwanted illumination in order to minimize the background. The XAS measurements are performed in the so-called flying scan mode where one scan of the spectrum is measured in 2 minutes⁵.

$\text{Ho}_3\text{N@C}_{80}$ molecules dissolved in toluene were air-brushed on top of wet-transferred graphene on 90 nm SiO_2 .

FIG. 2. (a) Sum of 15 XAS scans with 1000 data points measured at room temperature (red) and 100 K (blue). In order to determine the background, the spectra are fitted with 6-order polynomials in spectral regions without Ho contribution (grey bars). The corresponding background is shown for the 100 K data (dashed line). The inset depicts a $\text{Ho}_3\text{N}@C_{80}$ molecule. (b) Asymmetry $A = (I_{RT} - I_{LT}) / (I_{RT} + I_{LT})$ of the two spectra (a). One asymmetry value is determined from binning 10 data points. The dashed line is the linear trend of the background asymmetry (10 ppm/eV).

The air-brush process takes approximately 30 seconds. It provides a thin layer of molecules on the surface. From x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) after annealing to 400 K for 30 minutes, we estimate a C_{80} coverage of about one monolayer on the substrate surface.

In order to investigate a possible change of average molecular conformation with temperature and to benchmark the sensitivity of the ET detector setup, we performed XAS measurements on the $\text{Ho}_3\text{N}@C_{80}$ /graphene system at two different temperatures. The x-ray incidence angle is 10° off normal and the x-rays have linear p-polarization. The PMT current is recorded by a Keithley 6517B electrometer, with an integration time of 100 ms. The measured mirror current (not shown) is stable and decreases with photon energy as it does with the background of the spectra. Figure 2(a), shows two spectra that are the sum of 15 scans each. The first spectrum is recorded at room temperature (300 K) and the second after cooling to low temperature (100 K) across the Ho $M_{5,4}$ edges. Otherwise, all detector and manipulator settings are kept constant. A pronounced Ho signal is observed, where the signal-to-background ratio at the M_5 peak is about 1:7. The spectra identify Ho^{3+} species⁶, as in other holmium containing endofullerenes⁷.

For the background subtraction, the raw data are normalized with a background function, followed by subtraction of 1. The background function is obtained by a 6th-order polynomial, which is fitted to the part of the spectrum with-

out Ho signal (marked with grey bars in Figure 2(a)). With this procedure, we get an absolute M_5 spectral weight W_{M_5} of 0.90 ± 0.02 , where the room temperature data indicate for given support intervals slightly higher W_{M_5} values that lie in the confidence interval. We note that the 68% confidence interval of ± 0.02 mainly depends on systematic uncertainties due to the choice of the support intervals for the background subtraction (grey bars in Figure 2(a)), while for the shown measurements the random error for W_{M_5} is about 0.2%. The predicted Ho M_5 spectral weight from theory⁶ is 0.892, which lies within the systematic error of the measurements. W_{M_5} does not match 3/5 as it would be expected from the multiplicities of pure $3d_{5/2}$ and the $3d_{3/2}$ final states. Instead, it is indicative that the $3d^9 4f^{n+1}$ multiplet distributions into M_5 or M_4 are sensitive to the 4f occupancy⁶.

Figure 2(b) shows the asymmetry of the room temperature (RT) and the low temperature (LT) spectra $A = (I_{RT} - I_{LT}) / (I_{RT} + I_{LT})$. The standard deviation in the asymmetry spectrum is 0.1 % before binning. This value is obtained from spectral regions outside the Ho peaks after subtraction of a linear function. The offset of the background asymmetry from zero by about 1% is due to different photon fluxes as inferred from the photoemission current from the focusing mirror. The slope in the asymmetry of 10 ppm/eV in the spectral regions outside the Ho peaks indicates a weak difference in the photon energy dependence of the TEY for the two measurements. The asymmetry at the Ho M_5 edge indicates a 0.2% increase. This can e.g. be due to x-ray induced desorption of molecules or conformational change since XAS is sensitive to the orientation of the endohedral units with respect to the incoming x-rays¹.

The presented measurements with the ET set-up in Figure 2 show that changes in the XAS multiplet spectra may be obtained with per mille accuracy. It is furthermore expected that this set-up is also operational for x-ray circular dichroism measurements, as long as there are no external magnetic fields that would deviate the low energy electrons on the way from the sample to the detector⁸.

In conclusion, we performed XAS measurements on spray-coated $\text{Ho}_3\text{N}@C_{80}$ molecules on graphene with an Everhart-Thornley detector, which reduces the measurement time with respect to sample current measurements by a factor of 25.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Financial support by the Swiss National Science Foundation grant No. 200020_153312 and No. 200020_201086 are gratefully acknowledged. The Paul Scherrer Institut, Villigen, Switzerland provided synchrotron radiation beamtime at the PEARL beamline. We thank Ari Seitsonen for providing the image of the molecule in Figure 2.

Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- ¹R. Westerström, A.-C. Uldry, R. Stania, J. Dreiser, C. Piamonteze, M. Muntwiler, F. Matsui, S. Rusponi, H. Brune, S. Yang, A. Popov, B. Büchner, B. Delley, and T. Greber, “Surface aligned magnetic moments and hysteresis of an endohedral single-molecule magnet on a metal,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **114**, 087201 (2015).
- ²R. Stania, A. P. Seitsonen, H. Y. Jung, D. Kunhardt, B. Büchner, A. A. Popov, M. Muntwiler, and T. Greber, “Temperature induced change of conformation of $\text{Sc}_2\text{TbN}@C_{80}$ on *h*-BN/Ni(111),” (2022), 10.48550/ARXIV.2205.07342.
- ³M. Muntwiler, J. Zhang, R. Stania, F. Matsui, P. Oberta, U. Flechsig, L. Patthey, C. Quitmann, T. Glatzel, R. Widmer, E. Meyer, T. A. Jung, P. Aebi, R. Fasel, and T. Greber, “Surface science at the PEARL beamline of the Swiss Light Source,” *J. Synchrotron Rad.* **24**, 354–366 (2017).
- ⁴T. E. Everhart and R. F. M. Thornley, “Wide-band detector for microampere low-energy electron currents,” *Journal of Scientific Instruments* **37**, 246–248 (1960).
- ⁵J. Krempaský, U. Flechsig, T. Korhonen, D. Zimoch, C. Quitmann, and F. Nolting, “Synchronized monochromator and insertion device energy scans at SLS,” *AIP Conference Proceedings* **1234**, 705–708 (2010), <https://aip.scitation.org/doi/pdf/10.1063/1.3463307>.
- ⁶B. T. Thole, G. van der Laan, J. C. Fuggle, G. A. Sawatzky, R. C. Karnatak, and J.-M. Esteve, “3d x-ray-absorption lines and the $3d^9 4f^{n+1}$ multiplets of the lanthanides,” *Phys. Rev. B* **32**, 5107–5118 (1985).
- ⁷Y. Zhang, D. Krylov, S. Schiemenz, M. Rosenkranz, R. Westerström, J. Dreiser, T. Greber, B. Büchner, and A. A. Popov, “Cluster-size dependent internal dynamics and magnetic anisotropy of Ho ions in $\text{HoM}_2\text{N}@C_{80}$ and $\text{Ho}_2\text{MN}@C_{80}$ families ($M = \text{Sc, Lu, Y}$),” *Nanoscale* **6**, 11431–11438 (2014).
- ⁸M. Morscher, F. Nolting, T. Brugger, and T. Greber, “Resonant photoelectron diffraction with circularly polarized light,” *Phys. Rev. B* **84**, 140406 (2011).